

Schrodinger Equation from Fokker-Planck Equation and Contradiction Due To Interference? Part II

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Classical mechanics traces a particle's movement through space and time through $x(t)$. For example, one may consider the case of a particle moving at constant speed (momentum p) in one direction or a particle bouncing back and forth at constant speed in a box. These problems are described in time and have direction and position associated with time etc.

It is possible to define a probability $P(x,t)$ in the classical picture based on delta time, the amount of time a particle spends in a little region of space dx . $P(x,t)$, by itself, loses much relevant information present in the $x(t)$ scenario because a particle moving to the right, or to the left, or bouncing back and forth all have the same probability, $1/L$, where L is length. Furthermore, this probability is the same for all p (momentum) values. Thus a probability description, without extra information, is a subset of the relevant information in the problem. As a result, to describe the classical picture fully, one might say that a particle has a probability of $1/L$, but also a mass m_0 and velocity $+v$ (i.e. momentum mv nonrelativistically). For the particle bouncing back and forth in a box with constant p , one needs to give the initial position at time=0 and then a subsequent time (as well as the initial velocity and m_0) in order to fully describe the problem, even though probability = $1/L$.

In the literature (see (1)), there have been many attempts to derive the quantum Schrodinger equation from a classical Fokker-Planck equation or a continuity equation (which follows from the Fokker-Planck equation as shown in (1)). The continuity equation contains a probability $P(x,t)$ and a velocity $v(x,t)$ and is generally argued to represent classical physics. It does, if one retains appropriate classical conditions such as the discontinuity of density for a particle in a box (i.e. density=0 outside the box, but $1/L$ inside) and the notion of differing directions within the box. In fact, one may write density= $W^*(x,t)W(x,t)$ where $W(x,t)$ is an ad hoc complex function and still retain compatibility with classical physics.

If one does not, however, retain the classical conditions completely, nonclassical physics is introduced, even if density $\rho(x,t)=1/L$. For example, in quantum mechanics density $\rho(x)$ is considered to be continuous in all x . Thus for a particle moving in a box, density outside the box is 0 so at the box wall it must also be 0. In the classical case, the density is 1 inside the box and 0 outside. There is a discontinuity classically and this cannot be changed and this contradicts the quantum mechanical picture. Thus quantum mechanics does not follow from classical Fokker-Planck or continuity equations which retain classical conditions.. Furthermore, because time is completely removed in the FP-continuity approach as applied to quantum mechanics, one cannot distinguish between forwards and backwards motion. As seen by the velocity field given in (1), v is zero for a bound particle which completely removes the sense of time and violates the classical physics conditions. It is, however, not zero for a particle moving in one direction.

Thus there seems to be no issue in describing a Fokker-Planck-continuity equation as describing classical physics. One may even introduce density $\rho(x,t)= W^*(x,t)W(x,t)$ provided one retains classical conditions allowing for discontinuity in density and different $W(x,t)$ values at different times i.e. a discontinuity in $W(x,t)$ at a box wall. If these conditions, however, are not

met, then one no longer describes classical physics, but a new kind of physics (quantum physics). Thus one cannot argue that quantum mechanics follows from classical statistical Fokker-Planck-continuity equations. It may follow from these if one adds a set of extra conditions. Given these extra conditions, however, one could derive quantum mechanics without starting with classical density.

Classical Mechanics and the Notion of Probability

Classical mechanics follows a particle in space and time through $x(t)$. The direction of motion and velocity dx/dt are known and nonrelativistic momentum is $m_0 v$. This yields a full description of the particle in the classical view and may be applied to a particle moving either to the right or left with constant momentum or bouncing back and forth in a box.

It is possible to ask: What is the probability of a steady stream of these classical particles? In the above cases, the answer is $P(x,t) = 1/L$ where L is length. Time drops out of the $P(x,t)$ picture along with much other information such as speed and direction. In other words, a probability picture based on the amount of time a particle spends in dx is a subset of the information required to describe the classical viewpoint. One may use $P(x,t)$, but must “carry” extra information along if one uses a classical approach. One may not simply use equations for $P(x,t)$ which drop the other information.

The Fokker-Planck Equation and Continuity Equation

In (1) a Fokker-Planck equation is introduced as:

$$d/dt \text{ partial density}(x,t) = -d/dx \{ \text{density} * u(x,t) \} + Q(x,t) d/dx d/dx \text{ density} \quad ((1))$$

This equation contains x and t and is of a classical nature and so should carry the full information of classical physics.

In (1) a continuity equation is created from the Fokker-Planck equation, namely:

$$u_1(x,t) = u - Q d/dx \ln(\text{density}) \quad ((2))$$

$$d/dt \text{ density partial} = d/dx \{ v(x,t) \text{ density} \} \quad ((3))$$

$$v(x,t) = .5 (u + u_1) = u - .5 Q d/dx \ln(\text{density}) \quad ((4))$$

Here $v(x,t)$ plays the role of a velocity and should contain information about the direction and magnitude of the velocity for a particle moving in one direction even though $\text{density}(x,t) = \text{constant}$. In such a case, one would argue that the FP-continuity equation approach contains all of the necessary classical information. For constant motion, $d/dt \text{ partial density} = 0$, thus $d/dx \{ v(x,t) \text{ density} \} = 0$.

For a particle bouncing back and forth within walls, one would be forced to carry time with $v(x,t)$ to show that part of the time the particle moves to the right and the other, to the left. In this case, there is also a discontinuous $\text{density}(x,t)$ at the walls with the outside where density is 0 and the

inside $1/L$. Thus at this point there is no issue between the FP-continuity approach and classical physics.

Problem with Fokker-Planck-continuity Equation Approach and Classical Physics

As argued in the above section, the FP-continuity equation is consistent with classical physics if one insists on retaining the appropriate classical information. It seems, however, that approaches which try to obtain the Schrodinger equation from the FP-continuity equation violate these conditions and so do not represent classical physics.

Approaches which try to link the FP-continuity equation with quantum mechanics make the following ad hoc mathematical assumption:

$$\text{density}(x,t) = W^*(x,t) W(x,t) \quad ((5))$$

As shown in (1), the associated velocity is: $\hbar/i2m \{ d/dx \ln(W) - d/dx \ln(W^*) \}$ ((6))

If ((6)) represents the classical velocity, then $\ln(W) = px$ or $W = \exp(ipx)$. Thus ((6)) contains information about both forward and backwards motion. This is fine for motion in one direction which yields v or $-v$ for the velocity, but for a particle bouncing in a box with constant momentum, one would need to have $W(x) = \exp(ipx)$ for a certain period of time and $W(x) = \exp(-ipx)$ for another period. Furthermore there would be a discontinuity in density at the box walls. Thus one may use the assumption ((5)) and still retain consistency between a continuity equation: $d/dx (\text{density } v(x,t)) = 0$ and classical physics if one retains the above consideration i.e. $v(x,t)$ and density discontinuity.

The problem which arises seems to be due to the idea that $W(x,t) = W(x)$ i.e. one drops the time dependence of W for a particle bouncing back and forth in a box with infinite potential walls in the Schrodinger equation derivation approach. Secondly, one does not allow for a discontinuity at the walls of the box. This, we argue, contradicts classical physics and so must introduce a new kind of physics.

In the Schrodinger equation view, for a particle in a box with infinite potential walls, the density is 0 outside of the box. Thus $W(x,t) = 0$ as well outside the box. Inside the box, $W(x=L,t) = 0$ where $x=L$ is a box wall in order to have continuity of density (in violation of classical physics). Thus $W(x,t)$ must be real which means that velocity from ((6)) is 0. This again violates classical physics. The velocity is p/m part of the time and $-p/m$ the rest classically. As a result, a new kind of physics is introduced by forcing continuity of $W(x,t)$ and not including directional motion changes in time i.e. using $W(x,t) = W(x)$.

W(x,t) Introduced in an Ad Hoc Manner

Given that a number of classical constraints are violated when deriving the Schrodinger equation from the classical Fokker-Planck -continuity equation and $W(x,t)$ is introduced in an ad hoc manner and includes information about p (momentum) and a kind of probability in space, it seems one could establish quantum mechanics based on $W(x,t)$, and appropriate physical

assumptions (which are not classical) and then link it to density(x,t) without starting with classical density equations.

Conclusion

In conclusion, classical mechanics contains detailed information $x(t)$ about a particle and how it moves including its direction and speed. It is possible to ask: What is the probability $P(x,t)$ of such a particle? and find that for the case of motion in one direction or the other or for a particle bouncing back and forth in a box, $P(x,t)=1/L$ in all of these cases. This means that $P(x,t)$ alone does not represent all of the information in the classical problem. For the bouncing particle, one needs information in time, namely that one has p for part of the time and $-p$ for the other portion of a cycle. Furthermore, density is discontinuous. It is 0 outside the box and $1/L$ inside.

A classical Fokker-Planck equation may be used to write a classical continuity equation as shown in (1). One may go further and write, in an ad hoc manner, density $\rho(x,t)=W^*(x,t)W(x,t)$ where W is a complex function. So far there is no issue with compatibility with classical mechanics if one retains all of the classical information in $W(x,t)$. For example, even though density $\rho(x,t)=1/L$ for a particle in a box for all time, there is forward and backward motion and this information cannot be lost. A velocity field is written in (1) in terms of $\ln(W)$ and $\ln(W^*)$ and describes one directional motion classically. For the bouncing particle, $W=\exp(ipx)$ for half the time of a cycle and $\exp(-ipx)$ for the other half, to be consistent with classical physics. Furthermore, there is a discontinuity in density at the box wall because classical density is $1/L$ inside and 0 outside. As a result, a continuity equation taken from the Fokker-Planck equation and written in terms of $W(x,t)$ can still be consistent with classical mechanics if one retains the above classical conditions.

The problem is that these conditions are traditionally not imposed in moving from the continuity equation and density $\rho = W^*(x,t)W(x,t)$ to the Schrodinger equation. In particular, it is assumed that $W(x,t)$ is continuous in all x (which violates the classical condition allowing for density discontinuity) and that $W(x,t)=W(x)=\exp(ipx)$ instead of $\exp(ipx)$ for a half a cycle and $\exp(-ipx)$ for the other half. In this manner, new physics is established due to the breaking of classical conditions and so one may not argue that the quantum Schrodinger equation follows from the classical Fokker-Planck or continuity equation when extra assumptions have been imposed i.e. the breaking of classical conditions. If one breaks classical conditions, one has a new physics scenario which is not classical.

References

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